

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue III, March 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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**SELF-EFFICACY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TAGKAWAYAN
DISTRICT II, DIVISION OF QUEZON**

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ABSTRACT

Title : SELF-EFFICACY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN TAGKAWAYAN DISTRICT II, DIVISION OF QUEZON

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Keywords: Relationship, Self-Efficacy, Psychological WellBeing

This study investigated the relationship between Self-Efficacy and Psychological Well-Being of teachers between the two zones in Tagkawayan District II. Specifically, the study determined the level of self-efficacy of the public secondary school teachers in Tagkawayan District II along classroom management, instructional strategies and student engagement; the significant difference on the rank orders of the self-efficacy of public secondary school teachers between the 2 zones of Tagkawayan District II, the level of psychological well-being of the public secondary school teachers in Tagkawayan District II along depression, anxiety and stress; the significant difference on the rank orders of the psychological well-being of the public secondary school teachers between the 2 zones of Tagkawayan District II; the significant relationship between the self-efficacy and psychological well-being of the public secondary school teachers in Tagkawayan District II and formulated policy recommendations derived from the findings of the study.

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The researcher utilized the descriptive-evaluative-inferential-correlational method of research. It considered two (2) sets of teacher-made questionnaires for self-efficacy and psychological well-being of teachers. The respondents of the study consisted of one hundred forty-eight (148) public secondary school teachers of Tagkawayan District II. The statistical tools used were percentage, rank, weighted mean, Wilcoxon Mann Whitney U-Test and Spearman Rho. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Findings

The findings are summarized as follows:

1. The self-efficacy of the teachers which were rated "much evident" were Student Engagement, (4.24); Instructional Strategies, (4.20); and Classroom Management, (4.10).
2. The test of significant difference of the self-efficacy of the teachers between the two zones, the computed z values and the probability associated with the z, resulted to: Classroom Management, 0.19 and 0.8493 ($P > 0.05$); Instructional Strategies, 0.23 and 0.8180 ($P > 0.05$) and Student Engagement, 0.04 and 0.9680 ($P > 0.05$), thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.
3. The Psychological Well-being of the teachers perceived as "Fairly Evident" were: Stress, (1.83) and Depression, (1.78); while Anxiety, (1.42), was perceived as "Not at All".
4. The test of significant difference of the psychological well-being of the teachers between the two zones, the computed z values and the probability associated with the z, resulted to: Depression, 0.16 and 0.8728 ($P > 0.05$); Anxiety, 0.76 and 0.4472 ($P > 0.05$) and Stress, 0.35 and 0.7263 ($P > 0.05$), thus, the null hypothesis was accepted in favor of the alternative hypothesis.
5. The computed r_s and the t-values yielded to: 0.6616 and 10.66 ($P < 0.001$), thus the null hypothesis is rejected.
6. Policy recommendations formulated to improve the self-efficacy and psychological well-being of teachers were: Department of Education must conduct trainings to equip teachers with skills in handling most difficult students; Trainings to develop self-efficacy of teachers must be organized by the Department of Education to further improve teachers in delivering instruction; School heads must be aware of the health conditions of every teacher for early prevention of psychological and emotional disorders among them; Department of Education must provide activities and trainings to uplift the morale of teachers; District Supervisors should reflect on the feedback of teachers regarding their teaching conditions in order for them to implement activities which are suitable to teachers' needs; Policy makers must be considerate in recreating department's policies for teachers.; Local Government Unit must support teachers psychologically by giving them opportunities to perform their duties with ease considering their work arrangements in school; Inter-Agency Task Force must implement policies on

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT **Multidisciplinary e-Publication**

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ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

health and safety protocols; School heads must be observant about the behaviors and actions of teachers; Local Government Unit must provide incentives to teachers performing beyond expectation to develop their psychological well-being; and the Department of Education should regularly conduct trainings and seminars on stress management for teachers and school heads.

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions in this study:

1. The self-efficacy of teachers from the two zones is interpreted as "Much Evident" along: Classroom management, Instructional strategies and Student engagement.
2. There is no significant difference on the self-efficacy of teachers between the two zones along: Classroom management, Instructional strategies and Student engagement.
3. The psychological well-being of teachers from the two zones is interpreted as "Fairly Evident" along Depression and Stress and "Not at All" along Anxiety.
4. There is no significant difference on the teachers' psychological well-being between the two zones along: Depression and Anxiety and Stress.
5. There is a significant relationship between the self-efficacy and psychological well-being of teachers.
6. Policy recommendations are introduced towards quality education.

Recommendations

Pursuant to the conclusions stated ahead, the following recommendations were made:

1. Department of Education must spearhead trainings and seminars in improving teachers' self-efficacy in order for them to develop sense of responsibility and accountability in teaching.
2. School heads must encourage teachers to innovate and utilize variety of teaching strategies for maximized teaching-learning processes.
3. Local Government Unit must support teachers psychologically by providing assistance, incentives and rewards while understanding their working conditions.
4. Inter-Agency Task Force must consider teachers' duties and responsibilities in implementing guidelines about health and safety protocols in schools.
5. Department of Education must organize seminars and trainings about improving the psychological well-being and self-efficacy of teachers.
6. School heads must support teachers in all areas of their career in order for them to be motivated and confident in working despite pandemic.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10799276

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